

HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL SCIENCES

SOCIAL AND POLITICAL PROCESSES IN THE GANJA-KARABAKH PROVINCE AT THE BEGINNING OF THE 18TH CENTURY

Abbasli Kh.

PhD in History, Department of Humanities, UNEC

ORCID: 0009-0003-7499-3631

Baku, Azerbaijan

Abstract

In the early 18th century, socio-political processes in the Ganja-Karabakh province, which was part of the Safavid state, intensified centrifugal tendencies. The tax policy implemented in the Safavid state significantly influenced the socio-political life of the Ganja-Karabakh province and other regions. The central government lost its influence over the people, and high taxes, coupled with the tyranny of officials, resulted in political anarchy. The refusal of the population in the Ganja-Karabakh province to pay taxes resulted in clashes with government troops. The residents, who completely rejected tax payments, voiced their protest through uprisings. The weakening of government authority contributed to a rise in bandit formations across the country. In 1719, a significant popular uprising erupted in the city of Ganja and its surrounding areas, leading to the dismissal of tax collectors and other government officials.

An analysis of the events in the Beglerbeg during this period indicates that following the tax reform implemented by Shah Sultan Hussein, both the Muslim and Christian populations in the region ceased to pay taxes to the state treasury. During the period of paralysis in the Safavid state, local rulers assumed control over their regions. The Christian rulers of Karabakh not only refused to submit to the Safavid authority but also conducted raids on the local Turkish-Muslim population, robbing them of their resources.

Keywords: Ganja-Karabakh, Medieval uprisings, Middle Ages, Safavid state, Tax policy.

The late 17th century and the early 18th century were marked by significant political and economic crises in the history of the Safavid state. This crisis can primarily be attributed to the shift in traditional trade routes that connected the East and the West [2, p.48; 4, pp.64-68]. The economic foundation of many provinces within the Safavid state relied heavily on handicrafts designed for export to foreign markets, as well as income generated from transit trade. However, changes in traditional trade routes significantly undermined the economic power of the Safavid state. As a result, both trade and crafts, along with the production of essential raw materials such as cotton and silk, experienced a severe decline [8, p. 123-126]. The decline of trade and craft centers resulted in a significant decrease in both foreign and transit trade. To make up for lost revenue, the state and large feudal lords raised taxes on the population multiple times, which further exacerbated the economic crisis [3, p.56-63].

One factor that contributed to the economic decline of the Safavid state was the incompetence of Shah Sultan Hussein. The Russian diplomat Artemy Volynsky noted that Shah Sultan Hussein spent the majority of his time in the mosque and harem, leaving the governance of the state entirely to the discretion of the grand vizier [9, p. 665]. Polish missionary Judah Kruszyński described Shah Sultan Hussein as a ruler entirely disconnected from state administration, spending most of his time in entertainment [6, p.20].

To prevent the worsening of the crisis in the country, the Safavid ruler chose not to implement economic reforms. Instead, he focused on replenishing the empty treasury by increasing the number and amount of taxes. To maintain strict control over tax collection, a census was conducted across the country from 1699 to 1702.

Following the completion of the census, which was marked by significant violence, taxes were tripled and new taxes were introduced, including the abikuran, princely export tax, and six dinars. The task of collecting taxes from the Ganja-Karabakh province was led by Mirza Tahir, the grand vizier of the Tabriz province. His army of 1,100 men collected taxes at will, causing immense suffering for the population. According to Yesai Hasan Jalalyan, larger villages paid between 50 to 150 tomans, while smaller villages paid around 20 to 30 tomans. Taxes were imposed on merchants and all skilled artisans. Hasan Jalalyan, who directly witnessed and participated in the events of that time, provided an insightful account of the population census in the Ganja-Karabakh province. According to him, at the command of Shah Sultan Hussein, a significant number of officials, secretaries, and scribes were mobilized to register everyone aged 15 and older. The author describes the census as having been conducted using extremely harsh methods. Under the Shah's decree, anyone who attempted to evade the census would have their property confiscated and turned over to the informer, and those who hid could face execution. Additionally, officials who provided false information faced severe punishment—they were hanged by their feet, beaten, and fined [5, p.19-20].

The tax reform implemented by Shah Sultan Hussein not only failed to enhance the financial stability of the state but instead accelerated the collapse of the Safavid Empire. The tyranny of the Shah's officials, coupled with the heavy tax burden, placed the middle and lower classes in an increasingly unbearable situation. Consequently, popular uprisings erupted throughout the country. The local military-administrative system of the Safavid state, unable to quell these uprisings, became completely paralyzed.

The tax policy implemented by the Safavid state significantly affected the socio-political life of the Ganja-Karabakh province. The central government lacked the authority to enforce law and order across the country, resulting in limited influence among the people. An analysis of the sources indicates that the primary cause of the political anarchy in the Ganja-Karabakh province, as well as in other regions of the Safavid state, was the high taxes and the tyranny of local officials. This situation prompted the population to rise up and refuse to pay taxes altogether. The power vacuum resulted in a rise of bandit groups. Turkish author Alibey Badraddinazade provides insights into their activities. According to his account, individuals named Ganli Shaban (Bloody Shaban) and Molla Abdullah led a group of 2,000 people from four villages in the Jar region. They caused significant destruction and engaged in looting in the western part of the Ganja-Karabakh province for a period of three years. The author states that, over three years, they repeatedly attacked the districts of Tbilisi and Ganja at night, burned houses, forcibly took valuable jewelry from monasteries, captured women and children, and killed high-ranking officials [7, p.71].

According to sources, the refusal of the population in the Ganja-Karabakh province to pay taxes has led to clashes between residents and government troops. In some instances, rebels have confiscated and burned tax books to eliminate tax debts that had accumulated over many years [1, p.52]. In 1719, a violent uprising occurred in Ganja city and its surrounding areas. The rebels successfully expelled tax collectors and other government officials; however, local authorities ultimately suppressed the rebellion [5, p.21-23].

In the early 18th century, the primary focus of the struggle against Safavid oppression in Azerbaijan was the Shirvan Uprising. This uprising significantly influenced the socio-political landscape of the Ganja-Karabakh province. The increasing threat of the uprising spreading to nearby territories seriously concerned both the central government and the Ganja-Karabakh beglerbeg. This concern was not unfounded. Even before the Shirvan uprising, the ruler of Sakhur, Ali Sultan, and his troops annually attacked and plundered the provinces of Akstafa, Shamshaddil, Zayam, Shamkir, Ganjabasar, Kurekbasan and many villages around Barda, that were part of the Ganja-Karabakh beglerbeg [5, p.23-24]. In 1721, Ali Sultan attacked the city of Ganja and camped with a detachment of 8,000 men in the town of Sutokulan, which is located near the city. He was confident that he would easily capture Ganja. Ali-bek Badraddinazade reported that residents of Ganja, who were warned of the attack, surrounded, and eliminated all the attackers [7, p.74]. Hasan Jalalyan describes how the enemy army entered the city streets, prompting the townspeople to rebel. They blocked the enemy's path from all sides and killed more than a thousand soldiers [5, p.23-24]. The rebels persisted in their assaults on the Ganja-Karabakh Province, as well as the Kakheti Kingdom. Meanwhile, Ughurlu Khan of Ganja launched an attack against the rebels, but it did not yield positive results. After suffering defeat in the Battle of Shamkhor, Ughurlu Khan was compelled to flee and

seek refuge in the Ganja fortress. The rebels dealt heavy defeats to the Kakhetian king, Imamghulu Khan, on three occasions and ruthlessly plundered his lands [5, p.24]. Realizing that the situation was becoming increasingly perilous, the rulers of Ganja and Irevan sought assistance from Sultan Hussein, the Safavid ruler. The Safavid Shah, unable to fend off the growing attacks from the powerful Afghan tribes, could not provide any assistance. Consequently, the rulers of Ganja and Irevan decided to use their own forces to quell the Shirvan rebellion. In the autumn of 1721, an army of 40,000 men approached the Kura River to cross into Shirvan. One account of these events states that the rulers of Ganja and Yerevan were not successful in their first battle [10, p.77-80]. Under cover of darkness, the rebels stealthily crossed the Kura River and launched a surprise attack on the allied forces, successfully routing them. According to Jonas Hanway, this operation resulted in the Shirvan rebels seizing a significant cache of weapons and ammunition [11, p.81].

The events indicate that the leaders of the Shirvan uprising aimed to expand their influence into neighboring regions, especially the Ganja-Karabakh Province. This is evidenced by the attacks they launched in 1722. A contemporary of the events, Hasan Jalalyan, offers detailed information about a campaign that took place in April 1721. According to his account, the rebels who entered Karabakh from the direction of Bargushad caused significant destruction in the provinces of Dizag, Varanda and Khachin. The areas between the Gargar and Tartar rivers experienced the most suffering. The rebels captured many locals as prisoners and seized many cattle, sheep, and horses [5, p.29-30]. During this period, the Christian meliks of Karabakh sought to exploit the difficult socio-economic situation in the region to divide the state and establish a Christian state within the territory of Karabakh. The officials of the Safavid state in Northern Azerbaijan were fully aware of these separatist intentions and made every effort to prevent them.

Following the tax reform implemented by Shah Sultan Hussein, neither the Muslim nor the Christian populations in Karabakh paid taxes to the state treasury. Exploiting the weakened state of the Safavid government, local rulers effectively became independent. The Christian rulers of Karabakh not only refused to submit to the state but also organized raids against the local Turkish-Muslim population and robbed them. An eyewitness from that time reported that in Karabakh and Gafan, the Armenians, who were, in fact, Christian Albanians, united to attack the local Turks, mercilessly slaughtering them [1, p.54].

During this period, King Vakhtang VI of Georgia took advantage of the situation by moving to Ganja with the goal of eliminating Safavid control and annexing the region to Georgian territories. He ruthlessly plundered the beylerbeys. However, the Georgian warriors were primarily focused on looting and did not kill or capture the residents. They confiscated everything they could find. According to the rules, warriors were required to give the ruler one-tenth of the captured booty. From this booty, Vakhtang received 25,000 sheep and 9,000 cattle [5, p.33].

The administrative structure of the Ganja-Karabakh province, which was part of the Safavid state in the early 18th century, fostered the growth of centrifugal tendencies. The reliance of both the beglerbegs and the leaders of smaller administrative units on the central government was largely nominal. Simultaneously, the tension in social relations and the worsening economic decline typical of the Safavid state were clear in the socio-economic life of the Ganja-Karabakh province. The heavy taxation implemented by the Safavid rulers, along with the oppression from local officials, significantly worsened the conditions for the general population, leading to uprisings. During this time, the residents of the Ganja-Karabakh province experienced severe destruction and plundering due to attacks from both Shirvan rebels and Georgian troops.

In the early 1720s, the Safavid state effectively collapsed. A substantial portion of the country's territory was occupied by the Afghans, while Northern Azerbaijan and Dagestan were entirely beyond Safavid control. Although the situation seemed relatively favorable for unifying the territories of Azerbaijan into a single state, this proved impossible due to the weak connections between the regions and the intervention of more powerful neighboring states. Tsarist Russia and Ottoman Türkiye sought to exploit the power vacuum that arose in the South Caucasus due to the significant decline of the Safavid state, aiming to strengthen their positions in the region.

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